

Connecting Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs

Glocal Ecosystems

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Developed through the [EPIC-WE project](#), Connected QH Cultural Hubs are innovative spaces where diverse sectors and regions converge across countries to explore, co-create, and shape cultural heritage futures.

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Connecting local QH Cultural Hubs strengthens each partner's and site's knowledge production and innovation potential by connecting cultural expertise, materials, activities and perspectives, which is highlighted in this section.

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The section highlights the shift from local QH Cultural Hubs to connected hubs, and how they differ and relate in approaches, connections, and innovation potentials.

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Finally, it is emphasised how to get started with Connected QH Cultural Hubs, what is needed - and how to develop and sustain it.

01

In Short

This demonstrator expands the Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hub model to present a framework for **connecting QH Cultural Hubs** across sites to bring culture, industry, education, and citizens into cross-hub collaboration.

What

A *connected* QH Cultural Hub is a hub ecosystem developed in **EPIC-WE** in which youth citizens, cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and higher education institutions collaborate locally in their QH Cultural Hub while exchanging ideas, cultural materials, and creative outputs across hubs, regions, and countries. It links local hub imagination and innovation with cross-hub exchange, engagement, learning, and collaboration.

Why

Connected QH Cultural Hubs expand their cultural imagination, deepen collaborative creativity, and strengthen empowered youth participation. They allow local cultural practices and perspectives to meet those of other hubs, creating new cultural insights, expressions, and more connected European futures. Cross-hub collaboration nurtures cultural participation, experiments, and innovations in ways that no single hub can achieve alone.

How

QH Cultural Hubs *connect* through, e.g. common themes, tools, methods (as **EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit**), coordinating parallel or joint initiatives (as Cultural Game Jams), sharing experiences and perspectives (as in EPIC-WE Youth Advisory Boards), or exchanging products and outcomes. Each hub works locally within its own cultural site while connecting ‘glocally’ through co-operative platforms, cross-hub communication, collaborative cultural experimentation, and co-created initiatives and innovations.

Combined, connecting QH Cultural Hubs constitutes a tested framework for glocal, cross-hub partnerships and empowered cultural innovation.

02

What is a Connected QH Cultural Hub?

A **Connected Quadruple Helix (QH) Cultural Hub** is an intertwined ecosystem for cultural initiatives and innovation where youth citizens, cultural heritage organisations, higher education institutions, and creative industries work together locally to share cultural ideas, practices, and products with other hubs across regions, countries, and cultural contexts.

A Connected QH Cultural Hub **expands the core QH Cultural Hub model** developed, tested, and evaluated in the **EPIC WE project** by introducing an additional feature: the systematic linking of QH Cultural Hubs across sites. This enables an **intertwined and distributed cultural innovation ecosystem, focused on cultural co-operation, communication, and co-creation across interconnected sites, where each hub contributes** its own cultural heritage, communities, and partners, yet collaborates through shared themes, processes, and initiatives.

In this way, a **Connected QH Cultural Hub** is:

- **Local** – rooted in specific cultural partners, sites, materials, communities, and practices.
- **Glocal** – connected with other hubs through shared cultural themes, methods, initiatives, distributed innovation, and knowledge exchanges.
- **Transnational** – contributing to collective cultural learning, interactions, and cross-European innovation.

Within EPIC WE, Connected QH Cultural Hubs extend the quadruple helix ecosystem and living lab approach: Partners “meet in the middle” to form an “epic we” both within their local hub and through cross-hubs collaboration, co-shaping their cultural experiences, innovation processes, and value-driven cultural futures.

[Read about
Connected
\(Glocal\) QH
Cultural Hubs](#)

03

Why work with Connected Cultural Hubs?

Connecting local QH Cultural Hubs amplifies each site's potential by connecting cultural expertise, materials, activities and perspectives. This creates new forms of cultural learning, participation, and innovation that neither individual hubs nor isolated institutions could realise on their own.

1. Broaden cultural horizons

Local cultures and both tangible and intangible heritage meet across borders. Participants explore their own cultural contexts and how peers in other regions engage with cultural heritage, societal themes, and EU values.

2. Enable cross-hub cultural creativity and shared imagination

Shared themes, methods, and formats, such as EPIC WE's Cultural Game Jams, produce diverse perspectives, intercultural learning, and multiple interpretations of cultural themes. The "friction" between local and cross-hub differences sparks creativity, experiments, and new cultural practices.

3. Strengthen youth participation and agency

Youth become both partners and co-creators within their own local hub while also part of a transnational youth community that exchanges culture, collaborates, and participates across diverse sites. This positions youth as partners and decision-makers in cultural heritage and European futures.

4. Support institutional learning and innovation

Cultural heritage institutions, creative industries, and higher education gain insights into how cross-hub partners address similar challenges in different contexts, fostering experimentation, reflection, and the development of new formats, practices, and methods within and across sectors.

5. Support institutional learning and innovation

Connecting QH partners across hubs and countries nurtures a larger, shared cultural ecosystem. This strengthens cultural democracy, public value, and the ability to collaborate to innovate within Europe's cultural sector.

04

How to Create a *Connected* QH Cultural Hub: Step-by-Step

The [EPIC-WE](#) results demonstrate that connected QH Cultural Hubs can be developed through the following steps.

Step 1-2: Build & Collaborate

Connected Hubs follow the same foundational logic as QH Cultural Hubs, meeting in the middle, co-creating across sectors, and empowering youth, while adding intentional mechanisms for inter-hub exchange.

1. Create a local cross-sector partnership

Each hub begins by forming its Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub Partnership:

- Youth citizens
- Cultural heritage institutions
- Creative industries
- Higher education institutions

These partners create a shared space, **physical, digital, or hybrid**, in which cultural innovation can unfold.

2. Establish transnational connections between hubs

Hubs connect to other hubs through:

- Shared themes (e.g., **That's Not Fair!, Heritage Remixed**)
- Shared methods (e.g., **EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam Kit, E-P-I-C phases**)
- Shared environments (**online infrastructures, collaborative channels, shared resources**)
- Asynchronous exchanges (video messages, cross-hub feedback, design prompts)
- Synchronous encounters when possible (joint workshops, exhibitions, talks)

These connections create a **distributed cultural network** rather than isolated sites.

Step 3-4: Design and Experiment

3. Co-design connected and collaborative activities

Across hubs, partners work together to shape activities that feel both locally grounded and collectively meaningful. This involves defining:

- Joint themes that invite multiple interpretations across contexts.
- Common cultural questions that anchor exploration and dialogue.
- Shared timelines or parallel events that create moments of simultaneous engagement.
- Agreed methods and tools that offer a common creative language while allowing local adaptation.
- Cross-hub civic and community exchanges that bring different voices and perspectives into conversation.

By aligning these elements, each hub's activities contribute to a broader shared cultural inquiry rather than isolated local efforts. This ensures **each local activity contributes to a larger, shared cultural conversation.**

4. Run local co-creative initiatives with glocal scaffolding

Each hub organises co-creative activities rooted in its own cultural heritage, materials, and communities. These may include:

- Cultural-creative innovation events such as Cultural Game Jams, rapid design sprints, and cultural ideation and design workshops.
- Heritage explorations, artwalks, archive sessions, site visits, collection encounters, and experiments that invite testing, play, and reflection.

Although shaped by local heritage and context, activities are intentionally designed to exchange perspectives, enabling outcomes and **insights to travel between hubs** and feed into a wider connected cultural ecosystem.

Step 5-6: Connect and Iterate

5. Connect outputs across hubs

As activities unfold within each Connected QH Cultural Hub, the resulting cultural outputs, whether concepts, prototypes, methods, interpretations, stories, tools, or insights, are shared across hubs.

- Joint exhibitions, collections, or showcases, *physical, digital, or hybrid*, that place outputs from multiple hubs in conversation.
- Cross-hub reflection sessions, asynchronous commentary, or recorded exchanges that surface different interpretations and perspectives.
- Distributed documentation spaces, such as shared repositories or project platforms, that make emerging practices visible across sites.

These exchanges form a **living network of ideas**, enabling shared reflection, inspiring new iterations, and enabling approaches developed in one hub to meaningfully inform and enrich practices in another.

6. Iterate, reflect, and grow – locally and glocally

Connected QH Cultural Hubs evolve through continuous cycles of experimentation and reflection. Partners regularly assess both their local process and their cross-hub collaboration, asking:

- Which formats, methods, or approaches supported collaboration?
- What translated well across contexts, and what required adaptation?
- Where did new insights emerge, and how can they be carried forward?
- How can hub connections be strengthened or made more reciprocal?

Through ongoing reflection, hubs refine their practice and deepen their ties, gradually forming a **connected cultural ecosystem** that shares knowledge, exchanges ideas, and co-develops cultural innovation across sites.

05

The Connected QH Cultural Hub Ecosystem

The connected QH Cultural Hub ecosystem extends the core QH Cultural Hub “house with four pillars” model by showing how youth citizens, cultural heritage institutions, higher education institutions, and creative industries not only sustain the hub locally, but also remain actively connected across hubs, cultures, and regions. Each pillar continues to represent a key sector, yet the strength of the connected model and approach lies in the cross-cutting lines of exchange, collaboration, and cultural circulation that run between pillars and hubs.

Rather than standing as an isolated structure, the Connected QH Cultural Hub becomes part of a networked house, where ideas, practices, materials, agencies, and perspectives flow vertically and horizontally across sectors and borders. The interlinking connections turn the model into a distributed cultural ecosystem, one in which local uniqueness is preserved, but enriched and transformed through glocal collaboration and co-creative cultural innovation.

Within the Connected QH Cultural Hubs, innovative collaborations emerge across different social, sectoral, cultural and national worlds. It supports local and glocal connectivity, knowledge-sharing partnerships, and inspiration within and across sectors. While the sectors remain the foundation of the QH Cultural Hub, vibrant cross-regional and transnational connections enable new insights, relationships, practices, and cultural innovations.

06

Getting Started

A **Connected Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub** starts with a simple spark: curiosity about what happens when cultural, creative, educational, and civic actors share their work across sites and sectors beyond their immediate domain. Begin by gathering a small group of partners who see culture as something that can move, develop, and grow through collaboration. You don't need a formal structure or a large coalition to start. Pick a theme that resonates, a cultural question worth exploring, or cultural collections and materials that invite interpretation. **Create a light, adaptable initiative:** a short creative sprint, a cultural heritage remix session, a cultural lab, or a mini-jam that empowers people to express, experiment, and reimagine culture together. From the outset, include a “connected” and “connecting” aspect approach.

Share early ideas and prototypes with another hub or community. Invite a brief exchange session. Share a cultural prompt, challenge, value, or a cultural-creative initiative. Small acts form the connective tissue that gradually transforms local experiments into a wider cultural network. Treat each exchange as a rehearsal space. Notice which processes and formats foster collaboration, which invigorates and sparks new insights, and which moments broaden horizons. Pay attention to what is meaningful to your hub and what creates meaning for your partners elsewhere.

Bring in new partners, align processes and initiatives across hubs, or adapt an existing initiative for mirroring elsewhere. Over time, these iterative, interconnected efforts can develop into a **vibrant connected ecosystem**, one where cultural expression, youth participation, and cross-sector innovation naturally extend and intertwine across sites.

The key step is simple: reach out, connect, exchange, and start co-operating, communicating and collaborating together, locally and glocally across sites with each other.

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Want To Know More?

If you want to dive deeper into the EPIC-WE reports and publications to learn more about what Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs are, what they could become, and how they operate and create impact, see some of the following.

Report: Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation. EPIC-WE Quadruple Helix Cultural Ecosystems and Cultural Hubs

Paper: Meeting in the middle: Cultural co-creation, transformative partnerships, and ecosystems for public good

Report: The Impact of CGJs in EPIC-WE

Report: Game-Making Interventions with Youth in Cultural Heritage Institutions

Report: EPIC-WE Impact Guidebook

[EPIC-WE Resource Site](#)

Report: Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs, Cultural Game Jams, and Games through & for Culture

All EPIC-WE Reports on Zenodo

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